

"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT
VA TARAQQIYOT"

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI:
"O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI

23-24
OKTYABR

23-24
OCTOBER
2025

2030
UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL
AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS"

TOSHKENT DAVLAT
IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI

FORUM
"2030"
GLOBAL VA
UZBEKISTON -
2030
DUNYO DROHOL
TARAFIDAN
"YASHIL IQTISODIYOT
VA TARAQQIYOT"
STRATEGIYA
"O'ZBEKISTON -
2030"

GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI:
"O'ZBEKISTON - 2030" STRATEGIYASI

GLOBAL AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS: "UZBEKISTAN-2030" STRATEGY

ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ
ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ:
СТРАТЕГИЯ «УЗБЕКИСТАН -2030»

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT

2025

ELEKTRON ILMIY JURNAL

MAXSUS SON

- MACROECONOMIC STABILITY
- LABOR MARKET IN THE GREEN ECONOMY
- GLOBAL ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC RELATIONS
- GREEN INVESTMENT AND FINANCING
- GREEN TECHNOLOGIES
- ECO-TOURISM
- GREEN INNOVATIONS

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL
AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS"

TASHKENT
STATE
UNIVERSITY OF
ECONOMICS

2nd CONFERENCE
BANKING /
FINANCIAL
DIRECTION
THE PRIVATE

BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI
VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI
RIVOJLANTIRISH
YO'NALISHLARI

2030

**TOSHKENT DAVLAT
IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI**

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: “O‘ZBEKISTON – 2030” STRATEGIYASI FORUMI

(MAXSUS SON)

TOSHKENT–2025

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

ISBN: 978-9910-8110-8-1

UO'K: 004.89(575.1)(062)

KBK: 32.813(5O')ya1

T 97

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjayeich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayeich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhriddinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow))
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.11 Marketing
08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
08.00.13 Menejment
08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

INNOVATSION SIYOSATNI AMALGA OSHIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI – OLIY TA'LIM TRANSFORMATSIYASI, RAQAMLI MODERNIZATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH OMILLARI.....	13
Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich	
O'ZBEKISTON YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHI: ZARURAT, MAQSADI VA AYRIM MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLAR	16
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
FAN, TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRISHDAGI SO'NGGI TENDENSIYALAR VA INNOVATSIYALAR	25
To'ychiyev Olimjon Alijonovich	
QURILISH TASHKILOTLARIDA KREDITGA LAYOQATLILIKNI BAHOLASHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH	30
Mavlanov Normo'min Normamatovich	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA DAVLAT XARIDLARINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISHDA ELEKTRON SAVDOLARNING AHAMIYATI.....	37
Turabov Sarvar Abdumalikovich	
O'ZBEKISTONNI MINTAQAVIY TA'LIM VA ILM-FAN HABIGA AYLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	41
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li	
HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYALARIGA INNOVATSION KOMPONENTLARNI INTEGRATSIYA QILISH USULLARI	46
Muminov Fazliddin Xusniddin o'g'li	
OROL DENGIZI MEROSI: EKOLOGIK FOJIANI BARQAROR EKOTURIZM IMKONIYATLARIGA AYLANTIRISH	52
Zufarova Nozima	
KORXONALARNING YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYASINI ISHLAB CHIQISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	60
Ergashxodjayeva Shaxnoza Djasurovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISHCHI KUCHI BOZORINING TAKRORIY AMAL QILISHINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	66
Mamaraximov B.E.	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR VA MOLIYAVIY INSTRUMENTLARDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI GAROV DIVERSIFIKATSIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	70
Xolbozorov Husniddin Norbek o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA MARKETINGNING INNOVATSION KONSEPSIYALARI.....	76
Jumayev Olimjon Sadulloevich, Axmedova Shoxsanam Sindbod qizi	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA EKOLOGIK MAHSULOTLARNI TARG'IB QILISH VA SOTISHNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH USULLARI	84
Jalalova Dildora Jamolovna	
DIRECTIONS OF FORMING AND PROVIDING A COMPETITIVE EXPORT-ORIENTED ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN	87
Asatullaev Khurshid Sunatullaevich, Nasirxodjaeva Dilafruz Sabitkhanovna, Abdullayeva Madina Kamilovna	
FROM SCIENCE TO BUSINESS: HOW UNIVERSITIES STIMULATE INNOVATION	94
Prof. A. Bobozhonov, Prof. A.M. Shatre, Assoc. Prof. V. Kirilova Vladimirova, prof. R.Kh. Karlibaeva	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TECHNOLOGIES IN UZBEKISTAN BASED ON ADVANCED INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE	100
Otamuratov Sarvar	
SPECIFIC FEATURES OF MIGRATION FROM UZBEKISTAN AND PROSPECTS FOR ORGANIZATIONAL IMPROVEMENT	105
Sabiroya Lola Shavkatovna, Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	

KORXONA BARQAROR AXBOROT TIZIMINI YARATISH QIYINCHILIKLARI.....	112
Abidov Abdujabbar Abduxamidovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATIGA FOIZ RISKINING TA'SIRI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	119
Isakov.J.Ya	
CREATION OF A MECHANISM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND INTRODUCTION OF A MODEL OF COMPLETE TRANSITION TO THE NETZERO ENERGY SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN	127
Makhmudova Guljakhon N., Gulomova Nigora Farxadovna	
УСИЛЕНИЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОГО МЕХАНИЗМА НА СТОИМОСТНУЮ ОЦЕНКУ ОСНОВНЫХ ФАКТОРОВ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА.....	133
Алишер Расулев, Сергей Воронин	
РОЛЬ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ В РАЗВИТИИ МАЛОГО И СРЕДНЕГО ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА: ПЕРСПЕКТИВА И ПРИКЛАДНЫЕ РЕШЕНИЯ ДЛЯ ИХ ПЕРЕХОДА К МСФО.....	143
Эргашева Шахло Тургуновна	
DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS OF AGRICULTURAL ECONOMIC ACTIVITY UNDER DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	151
Boburjon Vafoev	
ENERGETIKA TIZIMIDAGI KORXONALAR MOLIYAVIY HOLATINING TAHLILI.....	157
Matnazar Yusupovich Raximov	
АСПЕКТЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЕМ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ.....	162
Очилова Хилола Фармоновна	
TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLAR.....	167
Abdullayev Suyun Artikovich	
THE INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN DIGITAL LEARNING PLATFORMS AND THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	171
Kuchkarov Takhir Safarovich, Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YANGI TEXNOLOGIYALAR YORDAMIDA BANK FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	174
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich	
РАЗВИТИЕ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА В РАМКАХ ПЕРСПЕКТИВ ВСТУПЛЕНИЯ ВО ВСЕМИРНУЮ ТОРГОВУЮ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЮ	180
У.А.Юлдашева	
ЗЕЛЕННЫЕ ПОТРЕБИТЕЛИ - ПУТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОГО РОСТА В РАМКАХ УСТОЙЧИВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	185
Дехканова Наргиза Шарифовна	
ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЙ АУДИТ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	192
Ходжаева М.Х.	
TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA AHOLINING MOLIYAVIY SAVODXONLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	199
Akbarova Barno Shuxratovna	
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH THROUGH TOURISM UNDER THE GREEN ECONOMY FRAMEWORK	204
Jumayev Akbar Mahmudovich	
МАКРОИQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHDA BANK TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	210
Erkinxojiyev Ismoiljon Ikromjon o'g'li	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA MINTAQAVIY SANOAT KORXONALARIDA KORPORATIV MADANIYATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH.....	216
Matrizayeva Dilaram Yusupbayevna	
UZBEKISTAN AT THE CROSSROADS OF HISTORY AND GREEN INNOVATION: FROM THE GREAT SILK ROAD TO A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE	220
Avalova Gulshod Murodullayevna	

ГЛАВНЫЕ ВЕКТОРЫ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ ПО ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	226
Абдуллаева М.К.	
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT IN THE INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN: MODERN TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS.....	233
Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna	
HUDUDDAGI KICHIK BIZNESNING SAMARALI TARKIBIY TUZILMASINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA MUTASSADI TASHKILOTLARNING O‘ZARO UYG‘UN HARAKATINI TASHKIL ETISH.....	239
Sharipov Kuvondik Baxtiyorovich	
BUSINESS ANALYTICS IN HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE: LESSONS FROM THE INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION TO THE DIGITAL AGE	246
Burxonova Sabo Tulanovna	
“COST ENGINEERING”NING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA UNI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHDAGI O‘RNI.....	252
Zaynitdinova Umida Djalalovna	
FEATURES AND WAYS OF FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	256
Kobilov Alisher, Majidova Irodahon	
ПИЩЕВАЯ ИНДУСТРИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: АГРАРНЫЙ ИМПУЛЬС, ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ И ЦЕНОВАЯ КОНЪЮНКТУРА.....	263
Юлдашев Голибжон Тургунович, Элдорбеков Гофурбек Искандарбек угли	
INCOME INEQUALITY AND MACROECONOMIC DETERMINANTS IN UZBEKISTAN: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS	273
Muhammad Eid Balbaa, Marina Sagatovna Abdurashidova	
РЫНОК ТРУДА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	276
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи	
EKOLOGIK QO‘RIQXONALARDA MONITORING JARAYONLARINING IQTISODIY VA TASHKILIY AHAMIYATI	282
Homidov Hamdam Hasan o‘g‘li	
ГАРМОНИЗАЦИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН В СООТВЕТСТВИИ С МСФО	288
Абдужалилова Дилноз Абдусаттаровна	
SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND BIODIVERSITY PROTECTION: CASE OF UZBEKISTAN WITHIN THE UNESCO WORLD HERITAGE FRAMEWORK.....	294
Yuldasheva Dilnoza Ulugbekovna	
ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ НЕЙРОМАРКЕТИНГА НА МАРКЕТПЛЕЙСАХ (WILDBERRIES, UZUM MARKET, ЯНДЕКС МАРКЕТ)	300
Юлдашев Жамшид Абрарович	
ЗЕЛЕНАЯ ЭКОНОМИКА КАК СТИМУЛ РАЗВИТИЯ РЫНКА ТРУДА УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	309
Шаюсупова Наргиза Тургуновна	
GLOBALLASHUV SHAROITIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANISHI O‘ZBEKISTONNING XALQARO SAVDOSIGA VA IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGIGA TAHDID SIFATIDA.....	315
Mamatov Mamajan Ahmadjonovich	
SUG‘URTA TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH VA INNOVATSION SUG‘URTA MAHSULOTLARINI JORIY QILISH MASALALARI	321
Xalikulova Gulzada Tadjimuratovna	
O‘ZBEKISTON OZIQ-OVQAT BOZORIDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI BARQAROR ISTE‘MOLNI RAG‘BATLANTIRISH	333
Eshmatov Sanjar Azimqulovich	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В РАЗНЫХ ОТРАСЛЯХ ЭКОНОМИКИ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ ОПЫТ И НАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ПРАКТИКА	337
Назарова Ра‘но Рустамовна, Мусаева Гавхар Ахматжон кизи	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA MEHNAT BOZORI: O‘ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	343
Homidjonov Fozilxon Umarxon o‘g‘li, Haydarov Kamoliddin Baratovich	

GREEN INVESTMENT: PATHWAYS TOWARD A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE.....	348
Odilova Sitora Sayfitdin kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARIDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	351
Kutbitdinova Mohigul Inoyatovna	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHGA TA'SIRI	356
Metyakubov Azamat Djumanazarovich	
ELEKTR SANOAT KORXONALARINING IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	361
Tursunxo'jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o'g'li	
УЧЕТ ЗАТРАТ И МЕТОДЫ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ СЕБЕСТОИМОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ	368
Махкамова Саида Гайратовна	
MILLIY HISOBLAR TIZIMIDA INTELLEKTUAL MULK MAHSULOTLARINI MAKROIQTISODIY DARAJADA HISOBGA OLISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSI.....	375
Sunnatov Muxtor Ne'matovich	
RENEWABLE ENERGY AND MACROECONOMIC STABILITY IN CENTRAL ASIA: PATHWAYS WITHIN THE GREEN ECONOMY	382
Khabibullo Abdullaev	
JAHON SUG'URTA AMALIYOTI ASOSIDA O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA BOZORIDA YANGI RIVOJLANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	387
Abdimovminova Saodat Taxirjonovna	
INTEGRATING DATA SCIENCE INTO GREEN FINANCING AND ECO-INNOVATIONS: ACHIEVING THE GOALS OF UZBEKISTAN-2030	397
Norboev Odil Abraevich, Kungratov Ilmurod Kuzibay ugli	
O'ZBEKISTONDA SANOAT ISHLAB CHIQRISHINI DIVERSIFIKATSIYALASH AMALIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	404
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
СОЗДАНИЕ ЗЕЛЕННОГО ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОГО КОРИДОРА В ЕВРОПУ: РЕГИОНАЛЬНЫЙ ПОТЕНЦИАЛ АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА, КАЗАХСТАНА И УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	411
Лала Гамидова Адиль, Арзуман Гусейнов Айдын	
MAHALLA TIZIMIDA AHOLINI OZIQ-OVQAT MAHSULOTLARIGA BO'LGAN ISTE'MOL TALABLARI MODEL.....	419
S. Qulmatova	
AHOLI ICHKI MIGRATSIYASINING MEHNAT BOZORIGA TA'SIRINI STATISTIK O'RGANISH	427
Mirolimov Mirislom Mirshokir o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BANK TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH TENDENSIYALARI VA MUAMMOLARI	434
Jumaniyozova Mukaddas Yuldashevna	
ЗЕЛЁНЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ТРЕНДЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	438
Фаттахова Муниса	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI SOHASI FAOLIYATINI DAVLAT TOMONIDAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH VA BOSHQARISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	444
Tuxtamishev Shodimurod Qurbonboyevich	
MARKETING TADQIQOTLARI ASOSIDA MEVA-SABZAVOT MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORT SALONIYATINI OSHIRISH	452
Xojiyev Elshod Yoqub o'g'li	
СПОСОБЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ НАУЧНЫМИ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯМИ В ЦЕЛЯХ ПЕРЕХОДА НА РАЗРАБОТКУ ЗЕЛЕННЫХ ИННОВАЦИЙ	459
Юдаков Александр Андреевич	
O'ZBEKISTONNI JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA A'ZO BO'LISHINING OZIQ-OVQAT XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHGA TA'SIRI.....	466
Axmedova N.A.	

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA KLASTERLAR FAOLIYATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI	471
<i>Sherkulov Shohruh Erkin o'g'li</i>	
DEVELOPMENT SCENARIOS OF UZBEKISTAN'S ACTIVE LABOR FORCE UNTIL 2030 AND THEIR ECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS.....	476
<i>Ganiev Bakhtiyor Zulfikor ugli, Rakhmonov Bekzod Sharibjon ugli</i>	
РАЗВИТИЕ ЗЕЛЁНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ КАК ФАКТОР СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ ЖЕНЩИН В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	481
<i>Дониерова Фотимабону Алишер кизи</i>	
YASHIL ENERGETIKA VA UNING IQTISODIY TARAQQIYOTDAGI O'RNI	488
<i>Babadjanova Malika Ruzimova</i>	
BENCHMARKING IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY: STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVENESS	492
<i>Abdurashidova Nigora</i>	
УЗБЕКИСТАН СТРЕМИТСЯ К УСТОЙЧИВОМУ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМУ РОСТУ, ВНЕДРЯЯ ПРИНЦИПЫ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ	498
<i>Сагдуллаева Гулнора Ботыровна</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN KOMPANIYALARNING GLOBAL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	502
<i>Sharipov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich</i>	
ZAIF BANDLIKDAN UNUMLI BANDLIK SARI TRANSFORMATSIYA: O'ZINI O'ZI BAND QILISH	507
<i>Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich</i>	
ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМАЯ ЭНЕРГИЯ В ГЛОБАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ТЕКУЩИЕ ТЕНДЕНЦИИ И БУДУЩЕЕ РАЗВИТИЕ.....	514
<i>Меҳрибан Самедова Тофик</i>	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING MEHNAT UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISHGA TA'SIRI	521
<i>Zafar Alisherovich Mamadiev, Nodira Isametdinovna Xasanxonova</i>	
SAVDO KORXONALARIDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA INTEGRATSIYA QILISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	526
<i>Ablazov Lazizbek Abdiquosimovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING TRANSFORMATSIYASI JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	530
<i>Ziyadullaev Z.</i>	
TO'LOV TIZIMI KONSEPTUAL MODELINING SHAKLLANISH TAMOYILLARI	537
<i>Toshniyozov Sherali Kamoliddinovich</i>	
STAFF PERFORMANCE EVALUATION BASED ON KPI SYSTEM INDICATORS.....	546
<i>Rakhmatullaeva Shakhnoza Khamidovna, Sadriddinova Sevinchkhon</i>	
SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC TRENDS	555
<i>Svetlana Yurievna Shatokhina</i>	
MILLIY TARBIYA OMILLARI VA MILLIY MADANIY YONDASHUV ASOSIDA TALABALARDA O'QUV TASHABBUSKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY-AMALIY ASOSLARI.....	560
<i>Azimova Nilufar Nuriddinovna</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARINI TA'MINLASHDA BANK RESURSLARINING ROLI	567
<i>Xodjayeva Jeyrona Ravshonbek qizi</i>	
O'QUV DASTURINI INTEGRATSIYALASH VA YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH: AKADEMIK VA SANOAT O'RTASIDAGI TAFOVUTNI YOPISH	572
<i>Qo'ziqulova Dilfuzaxon Maxammatisaqovna</i>	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND DIGITAL PLATFORMS AS A KEY FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS ENTITIES	580
<i>Rizayeva Nilufar Oblakulovna</i>	

IQTISODIY OLIY TA'LIMDA STRATEGIK INNOVATSIYALAR: YASHIL KO'NIKMALARNI MILLIY VA GLOBAL BARQARORLIK MAQSADLARI BILAN MUVOFIQLASHTIRISH	585
<i>Xasanova Zarina Maxamadaliyeva</i>	
MARKAZIY OSIYODA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT: BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH YO'LIDAGI TO'SIQLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	594
<i>Aminov Shovkat O'ktam o'g'li</i>	
ПЕСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЁНЫХ ОБЛИГАЦИЙ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	598
<i>Саидахмедова Аида Мирзаевна</i>	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ И СНИЖЕНИЕ РИСКОВ КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКОВ НА ОСНОВЕ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ТРАНЗАКЦИЙ В ФИНАНСОВЫХ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ СИСТЕМАХ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СИММЕТРИЧНЫХ КРИПТОСИСТЕМ.....	605
<i>Раҳимбердиев Қ.Б.</i>	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫХ И СТРАХОВЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ ДЛЯ СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА	612
<i>Ш.Ф.Кобилжонова</i>	
СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ КАПИТАЛА ХОЗЯЙСТВУЮЩИХ СУБЪЕКТОВ В КОНТЕКСТЕ РАЗВИТИЯ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА ЭКОНОМИКИ	618
<i>Д.А.Юлдашева</i>	
РОЛЬ БАНКОВСКО-ФИНАНСОВОЙ СИСТЕМЫ И СТРАХОВЫХ МЕХАНИЗМОВ В СТИМУЛИРОВАНИИ РАЗВИТИЯ ЧАСТНОГО СЕКТОРА	624
<i>Г.Т.Ахмедова</i>	
SUG'URTA BOZORI FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TRANSFORMATSIYALASH VA UNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI.....	630
<i>Saidov Farrux Faxriddinovich</i>	
OPPORTUNITIES TO ENSURE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE ENERGY SECTOR THROUGH THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY.....	635
<i>Ulashov Aliboy Rashid ugli, Istamova Nasiba Narzillo kizi</i>	
INKLYUZIV OLIY TA'LIMDA MUSTAQIL ISHLASH JARAYONINI TASHKILLASHTIRISH.....	641
<i>Akbarova Kamola Abdujabbor qizi</i>	
YOUTH-DRIVEN PATHWAYS TO GREEN EMPLOYMENT: A THEORETICAL EXAMINATION OF INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC STRATEGIES	646
<i>Suvpulatov Ozodjon Alijon ugli</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR VA UNING O'ZBEKISTON UCHUN AHAMIYATI	651
<i>Botirova Xulkar Olimjonovna</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH KLASTERLARI: NAZARIY ASOSLAR VA AMALIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	655
<i>Sherkulova Nodirabegim Baxordin qizi</i>	
BIOTECHNOLOGICAL SOLUTIONS IN URBAN PLANNING: OPPORTUNITIES AND LIMITATIONS OF "LIQUID TREES"	660
<i>Nosirkulov Asadjon Ahmadjon ugli</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TIKLANADIGAN ENERGIYA MANBALARINING O'RNI.....	663
<i>Fayziyeva Dilso'z Bahodirovna</i>	
KREDIT PORTFELIDA MUAMMOLI KREDITLAR ULUSHINI KAMAYTIRISH YO'LLARI	668
<i>Salixova G.J</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KANDOLAT MAHSULOTLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	672
<i>Boboyorova Maftuna Xaqqul qizi, Boboyorov Islombek Xaqqul o'g'li</i>	
OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH METODLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	675
<i>Xusniddinov Yorqinjon Muhiddin o'g'li</i>	

MODA SANOATIDA CRM TIZIMLARINI ELEKTRON SAVDO PLATFORMALARI BILAN UYG'UNLASHTIRISHDAGI TO'SIQLAR	679
Xalilova Nafisa Komilovna	
ENHANCING FOREIGN ECONOMIC RELATIONS AS A DRIVING FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY	683
Khaitova Feruza Bahrom kizi	
MARKAZIY OSIYO MAMLAKATLARIDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNING QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARIGA TA'SIRI	687
Akishova Shaxnoza Davlet qizi	
BUXORO VILOYATIDA HUNARMANDCHILIK FAOLIYATINING RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI: TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	693
Ravshanova Gulchexra Ravshanovna	
SANOATNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MEXANIZMLARI TURLARI VA OLIMLARNING YONDASHUVLARI	698
Ne'matov Shoxruxbek Ma'murjon o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA UNING XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI.....	703
Norova Nozima Nabiyevna	
O'ZBEKISTON BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMIDA REAL SEKTORNI KREDITLASH MEXANIZMLARINI SAMARALI JORIY ETISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJIGA TA'SIRI.....	709
Abduxomidov Ikromjon Maxamadin o'g'li	
MOLIYA TIZIMIDA BOJ-TARIF SIYOSATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA XUSUSIY SEKTOR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI (OZIQ-OVQAT IMPORTI MISOLIDA).....	715
Rizaev Mirmahmud Xotamjanovich	
YASHIL MARKETING VA ESG INTEGRATSIYASI: STATISTIK TAHLIL VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	721
Charos G'ayratova	
ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОГО КАПИТАЛА ДЛЯ ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА В УСЛОВИЯХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ «ЗЕЛЁНОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКИ.....	727
Г.А.Хайитбаева	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA TIJORAT BANKLAR TOMONIDAN TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI KREDITLASH.....	734
Tajiddinov Jamshiddin Shamsutdinovich	
IQTISODIYOTNING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASIGA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALAR TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	738
Shodiboyeva Dilzoda Farhodjon qizi	
MOLIYA TIZIMI BARQARORLIGI VA BUDJET TUSHUMLARINI OSHIRISHDA TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATNING AHAMIYATI.....	743
Aktamov Akbarjon Aslan o'g'li	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CARBON EMISSIONS AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT.....	748
Shakhriddinova Sitara Tolibjon kizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH JARAYONIDA TIJORAT BANKLARIDA INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA ESG TAMOYILLARINING ROLI	760
Ostonaqulova Gulchehraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT TAMOYILLARI ASOSIDA SANOAT KORXONALARIDA YETKAZIB BERISH STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	769
Yusupov Ulug'bek Mamayusupovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT KONTEKSTIDA MAKROIQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI MUSTAHKAMLASH: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI.....	776
Isroilov Islomiddin Kamoliddin o'g'li	

RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SPORT TASHKILOTLARINING YANGI BIZNES MODELLARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	782
G'ulomov Musirmon	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IQTISODIYOTGA XORIJIY INVESTISIYALARNI JALB ETISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI	786
Sharipova Shahnoza Baxtiyorovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA INVESTISIYA MUHITIGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA INVESTISIYALARNING IQTISODIYOTGA JALB ETILISH HOLATI TAHLILI	795
Karimova Qunduz Atanazarovna	
O'ZBEKISTON TURISTIK XIZMATLAR BOZORIDA BANDLIK TRANSFORMATSIYASINI VA UNI TARTIBGA SOLISH HOLATINI TAHLIL QILISH	804
To'xtayeva Xurshida Farxodovna	
INVESTITSIYA LOYIHALARIGA TA'SIR QILUVCHI INVESTITSIYA RISKLARINI BAHOLASH.....	811
Zohidova Ruksora Komiljon qizi	
ТИПЫ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РАЗВЕДОК: ОСНОВНЫЕ РАЗЛИЧИЯ, ФОРМЫ И МЕТОДЫ ОСУЩЕСТВЛЕНИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	817
Эсанов Шохрух Отабекович	
FACE RECOGNITION PROGRAM IN PYTHON.....	823
Khurramova Maftunakhon Zhurabekovna, Khurramov Azizjon Bakhodir ugli	
FORMATION OF ACCOUNTING POLICY FOR INTANGIBLE ASSETS.....	827
Farxod T. Abdvaxidov, Ramazon A. Abdurakhmanov	
O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORT TARKIBINI YUQORI QO'SHIMCHA QIYMATLI MAHSULOTLARGA O'TKAZISH STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	834
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
EKSPORT FAOLIYATIDA ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	838
Berdivaliyeva Madina Komiljon qizi	
TURIZM KLASTERLARIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLAR INTEGRATSIYASI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	841
Yazdanova Shohista Tuyg'un qizi Farxodova Shohnoza Umidbek qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON HAVO TRANSPORTI TIZIMINING JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	850
Azimova Moxinur Nozimovna	

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND THE TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL ECONOMIC TRENDS

Svetlana Yurievna Shatokhina

Senior Lecturer, Department of Macroeconomic Policy and Forecasting,
Tashkent State University of Economics, Uzbekistan

ORCID: 0009-0004-7388-4684

Email: sshatokhina165@gmail.com

Abstract: This article explores modern trends in sustainable economic development with a focus on the green economy transition in Uzbekistan. The study analyzes international practices and strategies for shifting to a low-carbon growth model, as well as evaluates the current state and prospects of renewable energy in the country. Particular attention is paid to green finance tools, ESG principles, and institutional reforms essential for Uzbekistan's integration into global sustainable development processes. Based on data from international reports and peer-reviewed publications indexed in Scopus, practical measures are proposed to accelerate the green transition and foster a resilient economy.

Key words: sustainable development; green economy; renewable energy; green finance; ESG; international experience; Uzbekistan; sustainable growth.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish jarayoniga e'tibor qaratilgan holda barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari o'rganilgan. Tadqiqotda xalqaro amaliyot va past uglerodli o'sish modeliga o'tish strategiyalari tahlil qilingan hamda mamlakatimizda qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarining hozirgi holati va istiqbollari baholangan. Shuningdek, yashil moliya vositalari, ESG tamoyillari va institutsional islohotlar O'zbekistonning global barqaror rivojlanish jarayonlariga integratsiyasi uchun muhim omil sifatida ko'rib chiqilgan. Scopus bazasida indekslangan xalqaro hisobotlar va ilmiy maqolalarga asoslangan holda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishni jadallashtirish va barqaror iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish bo'yicha amaliy takliflar ilgari surilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: barqaror rivojlanish; yashil iqtisodiyot; qayta tiklanuvchi energiya; yashil moliya; ESG; xalqaro tajriba; O'zbekiston; barqaror o'sish.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются современные тенденции устойчивого экономического развития с акцентом на переход к «зелёной экономике» в Узбекистане. Анализируются международные практики и стратегии перехода к низкоуглеродной модели роста, а также оценивается текущее состояние и перспективы возобновляемой энергетики в стране. Особое внимание уделено инструментам зелёного финансирования, принципам ESG и институциональным реформам, необходимым для интеграции Узбекистана в глобальные процессы устойчивого развития. На основе данных международных отчётов и рецензируемых публикаций, индексируемых в Scopus, предложены практические меры по ускорению «зелёного» перехода и формированию устойчивой экономики.

Ключевые слова: устойчивое развитие; зелёная экономика; возобновляемая энергия; зелёные финансы; ESG; международный опыт; Узбекистан; устойчивый рост.

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, the issues of sustainable economic growth and the transition to a green economy have acquired strategic significance. Accelerated globalization, climate change, the scarcity of natural resources, and increasing social inequality are setting new objectives for governments, requiring the search for effective development models. The concept of sustainable development, enshrined in the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (Sustainable Development Goals – SDGs), emphasizes a balanced integration of

economic growth, social equity, and environmental security. One of the key instruments for achieving these goals is the green economy, which focuses on reducing the environmental footprint of production and consumption, improving resource efficiency, and stimulating innovation.

For developing economies, including Uzbekistan, the shift toward a green development model represents not only an ecological necessity but also significant economic potential. Amid global economic transformations, growing interest in the ESG agenda, and expanding international partnerships, the greening of the economy could become a driver of long-term competitiveness. This issue is particularly relevant in the context of Uzbekistan’s integration into global economic processes, the diversification of its national economic structure, and the modernization needs of its industrial and energy sectors.

Despite significant international attention to sustainability and environmental issues, green economy development and its impact on sustainable growth remain underexplored in national scientific literature. This underscores the need for a comprehensive analysis of modern approaches to sustainable development and the formulation of effective strategies for green transformation, tailored to the socio-economic characteristics of the country.

The aim of this article is to analyze the theoretical and practical aspects of sustainable development, assess the role of the green economy in ensuring long-term economic growth, and develop policy recommendations for advancing green strategies in Uzbekistan within the context of global economic trends.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The development of a green economy and the transition to sustainable growth have become global priorities, supported by the Paris Agreement and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). According to research conducted by international organizations, effective environmental policies in emerging economies contribute not only to reducing CO₂ emissions but also to diversifying national economies, fostering innovation, and attracting investment [1, 2].

Studies focusing on Uzbekistan emphasize the country’s potential in solar and wind energy development, as well as the need to establish mechanisms for green financing [3]. Publications in leading Scopus-indexed journals highlight that the key drivers of energy sector transformation include institutional reforms, infrastructure modernization, and private sector involvement in sustainable development initiatives [4, 5].

Recent works also underline the importance of greening related industries – such as tourism, agriculture, and transport logistics – to achieve a systemic green growth effect [6, 7]. International experience demonstrates that integrating ESG principles into corporate governance and adopting innovative technologies enables Central Asian countries to strengthen their positions within global investment value chains [8].

Overall, the review of contemporary academic literature shows that Uzbekistan’s transition toward a sustainable economy requires a comprehensive approach: combining institutional reforms, large-scale investments in renewable energy, and the integration of international sustainability standards.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a systemic and interdisciplinary approach to analyzing sustainable economic growth and the green economy. It is based on comparative and structural analysis methods, enabling the evaluation of international experience and national strategies for transitioning to sustainable development [2]. Elements of economic and statistical modeling are applied to identify correlations between investments in green technologies, GDP dynamics, and greenhouse gas emissions [9].

The information base consists of official data from the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics, reports from international organizations (OECD, UNDP, World Bank), and publications in peer-reviewed journals indexed in Scopus. A bibliometric analysis of recent research was conducted to identify key trends and priority areas in the development of the green economy.

The application of this comprehensive methodological framework ensures the objectivity of findings and provides practical recommendations that align with international sustainability standards while taking into account the specifics of Uzbekistan’s economy.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In recent years, Uzbekistan’s renewable energy sector has demonstrated steady positive growth. The introduction of solar and wind power plants has not only increased electricity production but also reduced the dependence on traditional energy sources, contributing to energy balance diversification and enhancing the country’s energy security.

To assess the impact of investments in renewable energy on macroeconomic indicators, a correlation analysis was conducted examining the dynamics of capital investments, renewable energy production, and CO₂ emissions. The results revealed a strong negative correlation between the expansion of renewable energy capacity and greenhouse gas emissions (correlation coefficient $r = -0.78$), along with a moderate positive correlation with GDP growth ($r = 0.64$). These findings confirm the effectiveness of investments in the sector in terms of both environmental sustainability and economic development.

Key quantitative indicators are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Key Indicators of Renewable Energy Development in Uzbekistan in 2024

No	Indicator	Unit of Measurement	Value
1	Renewable energy produced (H1 2024)	billion kWh	1,6
2	Total renewable energy generation in 2024	billion kWh	13
3	Installed renewable energy capacity (end of 2024)	GW	4,5
4	Natural gas savings	billion m ³	1
5	Avoided CO ₂ emissions	million tons	1,4
6	Foreign direct investment (FDI) attracted to the renewable energy sector	billion USD	2,1
7	Projects in development	billion USD	13

The analysis shows that Uzbekistan is actively increasing renewable energy production and making significant progress in the green transformation of its economy.

In the first half of 2024, 1.6 billion kWh of renewable electricity was generated by ten solar and wind power plants with a total capacity of 2.4 GW, reducing natural gas consumption by 0.5 billion m³ [10]. By the end of 2024, total renewable energy generation reached 13 billion kWh, accounting for approximately 15% of the country's total energy mix [11].

As of 2024, the installed renewable energy capacity stood at 4.5 GW – about 16% of total power generation – resulting in savings of nearly 1 billion m³ of natural gas and the prevention of 1.4 million tons of CO₂ emissions. The sector attracted USD 2.1 billion in foreign direct investment (FDI), while projects worth up to USD 13 billion are currently under development. By 2024–2025, Uzbekistan had nine large-scale solar and wind power plants (1.6 GW), six hydropower stations (183 MW), and distributed generation panels (457 MW) installed at both social and private facilities [12].

Thus, the data analysis confirms that investments in renewable energy have a multiplier effect: the increase in the share of renewable energy to 15% of the national energy mix has been accompanied by a rise in foreign investment and a reduction in the carbon intensity of the economy. The obtained correlation coefficients further highlight the significance of the renewable energy sector as a key factor in sustainable growth and the ecological transformation of Uzbekistan's economy.

A comparative analysis with other Central Asian and Eurasian countries demonstrates Uzbekistan's rapid growth in the renewable energy sector. For instance, Kazakhstan generated approximately 6.4 billion kWh of renewable energy in 2024, accounting for 4.5% of its total energy mix [13], whereas Uzbekistan reached nearly 15%. Turkey, with an installed renewable energy capacity exceeding 58 GW, produces around 40% of its electricity from renewable sources [14], showcasing the potential for scaling similar technologies in Uzbekistan.

This comparison emphasizes that, despite a relatively small initial base, Uzbekistan is demonstrating one of the fastest growth rates in renewable energy development in the region and has significant opportunities to accelerate its transition to a low-carbon growth model.

The analysis results demonstrate that Uzbekistan has shown significant progress in recent years in developing renewable energy sources and integrating a green economy into its national growth strategy. Despite a relatively low initial capacity, the pace of increasing the share of renewable energy in the country's energy mix has outpaced many Central Asian nations, underscoring the strategic priority of sustainable development.

Global experience confirms that active investment in renewable energy and technological innovation contributes to diversifying energy production and reducing the carbon intensity of the economy [13]. The example of Turkey, where renewable sources account for approximately 40% of total electricity production [14], highlights Uzbekistan's potential to scale similar solutions.

An important driver of sustainable growth is the creation of a favorable institutional framework, including green financing mechanisms, tax incentives, and the integration of ESG principles into corporate governance.

Similar approaches have proven effective in the EU and China, where the transition to a low-carbon model has been accompanied by job creation and increased private investment [2].

For Uzbekistan, key priorities remain the development of solar and wind power plants, modernization of infrastructure, and the establishment of a carbon credit market. These measures will not only help reduce greenhouse gas emissions but also increase the country's competitiveness amid the global green transition.

Thus, the findings confirm that Uzbekistan's transition to sustainable energy is not only an environmental but also an economic priority. The development of the renewable energy sector has the potential to become a driver of innovation-driven growth, integration into international markets, and improved investment attractiveness of the country.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this study highlight Uzbekistan's high potential in the development of renewable energy sources (RES) and sustainable economic growth. Achievements such as the increasing share of green energy, active investment attraction, and CO₂ emission reduction confirm the effectiveness of the chosen development strategy. However, the transition to a green economy requires institutional innovation and robust financial mechanisms.

Recommendations:

1. Develop a National Decarbonization Roadmap with clear emission reduction targets and milestones for renewable energy integration. This aligns with the Uzbekistan Country Climate and Development Report [1], which emphasizes the importance of defining a long-term carbon neutrality strategy by 2060.

2. Introduce a comprehensive green financing mechanism, including the issuance of green bonds and the creation of a national carbon market. The OECD report Financing Uzbekistan's Green Transition [2] highlights the potential of thematic bonds to attract private capital for green infrastructure development.

3. Continue advancing solar energy policies. According to Solar Energy Policy in Uzbekistan: A Roadmap [3], a priority area is the gradual introduction of regulatory frameworks to increase the share of solar power and enhance grid flexibility.

4. Strengthen cross-sectoral cooperation and institutional reforms by leveraging the World Bank's Towards a Greener Economy in Uzbekistan action plan through 2030 [15].

5. Enhance human capital development by organizing training and outreach programs on green bonds and their impact assessment. In mid-2024, UNDP, the EU, and AFD conducted a seminar on these issues [16], demonstrating strong international interest and readiness to scale green financing tools.

Overall, the development of the green economy in Uzbekistan is becoming an integral part of the national strategy for sustainable growth and integration into the global economic landscape. Systematic implementation of renewable energy, ESG approaches, and sustainable finance tools will strengthen the country's competitiveness, reduce reliance on fossil fuels, and ensure long-term environmental security. The successful implementation of the proposed measures will require coordinated efforts from the government, business sector, and academic community, creating a solid foundation for building an innovative and resilient economy of the future.

List of used literature

1. World Bank. Uzbekistan Country Climate and Development Report (CCDR): Decarbonizing economy by 2060 [online]. 2023. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/uzbekistan/publication/ccdr> (accessed 03 September 2025).
2. OECD. Financing Uzbekistan's Green Transition: Capital Market Development and Opportunities for Green Bond Issuance [online]. OECD Publishing, 2023. DOI: 10.1787/27d2489d-en. Available at: https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/2023/12/financing-uzbekistan-s-green-transition_6ebf6b94.html (accessed 03 September 2025).
3. IEA. Solar Energy Policy in Uzbekistan: A Roadmap [online]. International Energy Agency (IEA), 2022. Available at: <https://www.iea.org/reports/solar-energy-policy-in-uzbekistan-a-roadmap> (accessed 03 September 2025).
4. Butaboev, M., Akhunova, Sh. Uzbekistan's transition strategy to a "green" economy and its significance. Res Militaris, 2023. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375121217_Uzbekistan%27s_Transition_Strategy_to_a_Green_Economy_and_Its_Significance (accessed 03 September 2025).
5. Isakulova, B., Usmanova, L., Saidvaliyeva, D. Transition to a Green Economy in Uzbekistan: Prospects and Challenges for the Development of Renewable Energy. E3S Web of Conferences, CONGREENTAX-2024, Vol. 574. 2024. DOI: 10.1051/e3sconf/202457401004. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202457401004> (accessed 03 September 2025).
6. Abdurakhmanova, A. The economic and social impacts of ecotourism on local employment and income in the rural areas of Samarkand, Uzbekistan. Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management, 2025. DOI: 10.1016/j.jhtm.2025.02.017. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1757780225000101> (accessed 02 September 2025).
7. Ahn, Y. J. Green spaces in Uzbekistan: Historical heritage and relevance to sustainable development. Sustainable Cities and Society, 2023. DOI: 10.1016/j.scs.2023.103029. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2772411523000290> (accessed 02 September 2025)

8. Imtiaz, A. A bibliometric analysis of global research trends and policies. *SN Business & Economics*, 2025. DOI: 10.1080/23322039.2025.2507135. Available at: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/23322039.2025.2507135> (accessed 02 September 2025).
9. Ochilov, S. The Relationship between Green Economy and Macroeconomic Stability in Uzbekistan. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2023, Vol. 2(5), pp. 882–893.
10. Uzbekistan discloses volume of green energy production in 1H 2024 [online]. *Trend.Az*. 19 July 2024. Available at: <https://www.trend.az/casia/uzbekistan/3980861.html> (accessed 02 September 2025).
11. Green energy becomes one of the drivers of our economy and a truly national movement [online]. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 28 February 2024. Available at: <https://president.uz/en/lists/view/6924> (accessed 02 September 2025).
12. Uzbekistan: the fastest-growing green energy player in the region [online]. *QazaqGreen*. 2024. Available at: <https://qazaqgreen.kz/> (accessed 02 September 2025).
13. Renewable Energy Statistics 2025 [online]. International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA). 2025. Available at: <https://irena.org> (accessed 02 September 2025).
14. Renewables 2025: Analysis and Forecast to 2030 [online]. International Energy Agency (IEA). 2025. Available at: <https://iea.org> (accessed 02 September 2025).
15. World Bank. Towards a Greener Economy in Uzbekistan: Action Plan on the Transition to a Green Economy and Ensuring Green Growth Until 2030 [online]. 2022. Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/results/2023/10/26/uzbekistan-realizing-an-inclusive-green-growth-transition> (accessed 03 September 2025).
16. UNDP; EU; AFD. Workshop on Green Bonds Impact Monitoring and Reporting in Uzbekistan [Электронный ресурс]. 02.08.2024. Available at: <https://www.undp.org/uzbekistan/news/undp-eu-and-afd-helps-government-uzbekistan-green-bonds-impact-monitoring-and-reporting> (accessed 02 September 2025).

**TOSHKENT DAVLAT
IQTISODIYOT UNIVERSITETI**

IV GLOBAL VA MILLIY IQTISODIYOT TRENDLARI: “O‘ZBEKISTON – 2030” STRATEGIYASI FORUMI

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT VA TARAQQIYOT

Ilmiy elektron jurnal

(MAXSUS SON)

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o‘g‘li

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug‘bek tumani
Kumushkon ko‘chasi, 26-uy.

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS
AND MATHEMATICS

23-24

OCTOBER
2030

23-24
OCTOBER
2025

1st CONFERENCE:
DIRECTIONS FOR ENSURING
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC
GROWTH IN THE CONTEXT OF
TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY

3RD CONFERENCE:
MACHINE LEARNING AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE:
A NEW APPROACH TO ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL
AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS"

UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY
23-24 OCTOBER

- ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES
- ECONOMETRICS AND
BUSINESS ANALYTICS
- DATA SCIENCE (DATABASES)
- DIGITAL GOVERNMENT
- DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION
- ECONOMIC STATISTICS
- QUANTITATIVE MEASUREMENT
OF THE ECONOMY

2nd CONFERENCE:
BANKING AND
FINANCIAL SYSTEM AND
DIRECTIONS FOR DEVELOPING
THE PRIVATE SECTOR

23-24 2025
OCTOBER

- Makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik
- Yashil iqtisodiyotda
mehnat bozori
- Jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro
iqtisodiy munosabatlar
- Yashil investitsiya va kreditlash
- Yashil texnologiyalar
- Eko turizm
- Yashil innovatsiyalar

СТРАТЕГИЯ
«УЗБЕКИСТАН –2030»

23-24 2025
OCTOBER

- Makroiqtisodiy barqarorlik
- Yashil iqtisodiyotda
mehnat bozori
- Jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro
iqtisodiy munosabatlar
- Yashil investitsiya va kreditlash
- Yashil texnologiyalar
- Eko turizm
- Yashil innovatsiyalar

strategy2025.tsue.uz

YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH
SHAROITIDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY
O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH YO'NALISHLARI

2030

<https://strategy2025.tsue.uz/>

TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS
ФОРУМ UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY

ISSN: 2992-8982

Elektron pochta: sq1141983@gmail.com

Telefon: +998 93 124 57 11

Sayt: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Telegram: https://t.me/taraqqiyot_va_talim_uz

ISBN 978-9910-8110-8-1

9 789910 811081

CONFERENCE "GLOBAL
AND NATIONAL ECONOMIC
TRENDS"

1st CONFERENCE:
DIRECTIONS FOR ENSURING
SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC
GROWTH IN THE CONTEXT OF
TRANSITION TO A GREEN ECONOMY

2030
UZBEKISTAN
STRATEGY

BANK-MOLIYA TIZIMI
VA XUSUSIY SEKTORNI
RIVOJLANTIRISH
YO'NALISHLARI